

THE BEHAVIOUR OF ELECTROLYTES IN MIXED SOLVENTS. PART II.
 VISCOSITY OF POTASSIUM CHLORIDE IN METHYL
 ALCOHOL — WATER MIXTURES AT 35°

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The present investigation comprises the study of viscosity of KCl solutions in 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50% by weight of MeOH-H₂O mixtures. The experimental data fit in well with the Jones-Dole equation:

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC.$$

While up to 30% composition *B* does not show any significant change with the composition of the solvent, its dependence on the composition of the solvent has been observed in the case of 40% and 50% mixtures. The nature and the composition of the sphere of solvation are suggested to be responsible for the magnitude of *B*.

In extension of our previous investigation (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 56) we have examined the viscosity behaviour of potassium chloride in methyl alcohol-water mixtures.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Potassium chloride and methyl alcohol used were of E. Merck 'extra pure' quality. KCl was purified as described previously (*loc. cit.*). Traces of water from methyl alcohol were removed by putting it in contact with freshly fired CaO for 4 days. It was distilled and was immediately put to use: the first and the last fractions were always rejected. The other experimental details have been described before (*loc. cit.*).

TABLE I
 Temp. = 35°.

Conc. (g. mol./litre).	η/η_0 .	MeOH: H ₂ O=50:50. $A=0.0071$.			MeOH: H ₂ O=40:60. $A=0.0065$.			
		$1+A\sqrt{C}$.	<i>BC</i> .	<i>B</i> .	η/η_0 .	$1+A\sqrt{C}$.	<i>BC</i> .	<i>B</i> .
0.010	1.0014	1.0007	0.0007 g.	0.070	1.0006	1.0007	...	...
0.025	1.0025	1.0011	0.0014	0.056	1.0013	1.0010	0.0003	0.012
0.050	1.0045	1.0016	0.0029	0.058	1.0022	1.0014	0.0008	0.016
0.075	1.0064	1.0020	0.0044	0.059	1.0031	1.0018	0.0013	0.017
0.100	1.0083	1.0023	0.0050	0.060	1.0040	1.0020	0.0020	0.020
0.125	1.0101	1.0025	0.0076	0.061	1.0048	1.0023	0.0025	0.020
0.150	1.0119	1.0028	0.0091	0.061	1.0056	1.0025	0.0031	0.021
0.175	1.0137	1.0030	0.0107	0.061	1.0055	1.0027	0.0038	0.022
0.200	1.0155	1.0032	0.0123	0.061	1.0073	1.0029	0.0044	0.022
Mean 0.061				Mean 0.020				

TABLE I (contd.)

[M and H refer respectively to MeOH and H₂O]

*Conc. (g. mol./litre).	η/η_0	$1+A\sqrt{C}$	BC	η/η_0	$1+A\sqrt{C}$	BC	η/η_0	$1+A\sqrt{C}$	BC
	M:H = 30:70. A = 0.058.			M:H = 20:80. A = 0.0054.			M:H = 10:90. A = 0.0051.		
0.010	1.0001	1.0006	-0.0005	1.0001	1.0005	-0.0004	1.0005	1.0005	...
0.025	1.0005	1.0009	-0.0004	1.0005	1.0009	-0.0004	1.0008	1.0008	...
0.050	1.0011	1.0013	-0.0002	1.0004	1.0012	-0.0008	1.0011	1.0011	...
0.075	1.0016	1.0016	±0.000	1.0007	1.0015	-0.0008	1.0015	1.0014	0.0001
0.100	1.0022	1.0018	0.0004	1.0008	1.0017	-0.0009	1.0016	1.0016	0.0003
0.125	1.0022	1.0021	0.0001	1.0013	1.0019	-0.0006	1.0018	1.0018	...
0.150	1.0028	1.0023	0.0005	1.0016	1.0021	-0.0005	1.0022	1.0020	0.0008
0.175	1.0030	1.0024	0.0006	1.0019	1.0022	-0.0006	1.0022	1.0021	0.0001
0.200	1.0033	1.0026	0.0007	1.0019	1.0024	-0.0005	1.0022	1.0023	-0.0001

TABLE II

Temp. = 35°.

Conc. (g. mol./litre).	Λ_0 ohms ⁻¹	Λ_0 ohm ⁻¹								
	M:H = 50:50.		M:H = 40:60.		M:H = 30:70.		M:H = 20:80.		M:H = 10:90.	
0.0100	90.80	—	91.90	—	103.70	—	115.8	—	139.2	—
0.0075	91.35	—	93.40	—	104.30	—	117.7	—	139.5	—
0.0050	91.90	94.6	93.90	97.5	105.05	108.7	118.6	124.2	139.7	141.3
0.0025	92.55	—	94.85	—	106.10	—	120.1	—	139.95	—
0.0010	94.30	—	95.80	—	106.90	—	121.3	—	140.5	—

180.42 *

* The figure refers to the zero composition of the mixture *i.e.*, containing only water (Benson and Gordon, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, 13, 473).

DISCUSSION

The relative viscosity η/η_0 for each of the concentrations of KCl in different mixtures was directly determined. For the evaluation of the constant A of the Jones-Dole equation

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

the dielectric constant data given by Åkerlöf (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4125) and the conductance data shown in Table II have been used. The value of B was estimated for each concentration of the electrolyte on substitution of the calculated value of A and the measured value of η/η_0 in equation (1). The results are represented in Table I. From these data it can be seen that there is no regular change in the product BC with the change of concentration of KCl in solvents containing methyl alcohol up to 30%; but the product BC shows a regular change with the concentration in cases of solvents containing 40% and 50% of methyl alcohol. This behaviour can be satisfactorily explained by assuming that B has no significant contribution up to 30% composition of methyl alcohol. For such compositions, the equation (1) reduces to $\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C}$.

It has been reported by Chakravarti (this *Journal*, 1943, 20, 41) that the constant B is almost zero for aqueous solutions of KCl at 35°. Therefore it can safely be stated that the behaviour of KCl solution in these mixed solvents up to 30% of methyl alcohol is similar to that of water. A positive value of B for 40% and 50% composition of methyl alcohol indicates that the Jones-Dole equation containing the term BC is applicable for higher composition mixtures.

From our study of viscosity of KCl solutions in dioxane-water mixtures (*loc. cit.*), we are of opinion that the magnitude of B is related to the nature of the sphere of solvation. The inadmissibility of the term involving B for 10, 20 and 30% composition mixtures indicates that the nature of the sphere of solvation is not materially altered by the presence of methyl alcohol molecules. The same conclusion has been arrived at by Amis (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1956, 60, 428) from his study of the conductance of KCl in MeOH-H₂O mixtures. At higher compositions of the solvent the MeOH molecules play a significant part in determining the nature and composition of the sphere of solvation. This expectation is justified by the fact that there is a regular increase in the value of B with the increase in the composition of the non-aqueous solvent, as has been observed in 40% and 50% mixtures.

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